

River Water Sample Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	What was the GPS location of the river sample?	Latitude Longitude
6	What was the GPS reference number	
7	Were you taken to the river by a household member?	Yes No
8	Physical description of the river site?	
9	What is the turbidity of the river water?	Clear Cloudy (mild) Cloudy (moderate) Cloudy (severe)
10	What is the river flow rate?	Slow Medium Fast
11	What is the river water colour?	Absent Present (light) Present (moderate) Present (dark)
12	What is the river depth?	<1m >1m
13	River temperature (<i>optional</i>)	_____ °C
14	River salinity (<i>optional</i>)	
15	River dissolved Oxygen (<i>optional</i>)	
16	River pH (<i>optional</i>)	
17	Was 500ml collected?	Yes No
18	What is the reason for river water usage in the house?	Household Drinking Household Cooking Household Cleaning (utensils) Household Cleaning (clothes)

		Household Bathing (of participants) Household Playing (of children) Household Commuting (adult) Household Commuting (child) Not used by the household
	<i>You have completed data collection for this sample.</i>	
19	Staff signature	
20	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY